

Website/D7.1

WP7, T 7.4

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Technical references

Project Acronym	RECONSTRUCT
Project Title	A Territorial Construction System for a Circular Low-Carbon Built Environment
GA number	101082265
Project Coordinator	Kathleen Blanco Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción de Cataluña Head of Innovation Project Management Department kblanco@itec.cat
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Actual submission date	21 November 2023

* PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)

SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Table of contents

Technical references	2
Table of contents	4
1. Executive summary	5
2. Overview	6
2.1. Graphic design	6
3. Contents and features	9
3.1. Landing page	9
3.2. Website development and sections	11
4. Other features	13
5. Dissemination	14
6. Conclusions	15

List of Figures

Figure 1. Website home page	8
Figure 2. RECONSTRUCT landing page	10
Figure 3. Website tree map	12

1. Executive summary

The purpose of the current report, D7.1 Website, is to provide evidence of the process followed during the development of the RECOSTRUCT website. The layout of the website is designed in accordance with the project's visual identity, as defined in the RECOSTRUCT brand book, which is illustrated in D7.2 Plan of the Dissemination and Communication Activities - 1st version.

The project website will be maintained in English and will serve as the primary source of information regarding project activities and results. It will be updated regularly with project documents, news, resources, and events. To facilitate communication between the project and local citizens and stakeholders, pages in local languages will be added in the building demo pages – this is the case for the Barcelona case study, while it has been chosen not to translate the contents for the Brussels case study. This initiative aims to remove linguistic barriers and promote effective communication with local audiences.

ICONS will support cross-linking with partner organizations' websites and other external platforms, fellow projects, and initiatives to increase clustering activities.

The layout has been designed in view of maximising the use of graphical elements, respecting the project's visual identity and tone of voice defined.

The release of the website was accomplished with the project work plan timing, M6 (November 2023). Modifications can be made to content and images (e.g. demo cases). The stakeholder's platform link will be added when available.

2. Overview

The final project website was launched on November 2023. It is accessible at the following link: www.reconstruct-project.eu

The website is a reference for all the activities implemented in the project as well as an entry point to RECONSTRUCT addressing different target audiences: Policymakers and public authorities, Construction value chain actors, Software technology developers and providers, Hardware technology manufacturers and providers, Data Management companies, Technology service providers, Financial actors and investors, Clusters, associations, and interest groups, Research & academia, Civil society, Media. The website contains both institutional and scientific information about the project and serves as a channel for communicating and disseminating the project's results.

The website will serve as our primary platform to showcase the project's work. As the official RECONSTRUCT portal, it will be the central hub for stakeholders and the public to access information on the project's activities, outcomes, and stakeholder engagement initiatives.

The website is a constantly evolving tool that will be updated regularly with new content, graphic layouts, tools, and features as per the project's requirements. The "News & Events" page will be updated frequently by ICONS with the support of project partners. The aim is to keep the texts simple, scientifically accurate, and easily understandable by a wide range of audiences.

The website is designed inclusively for all viewers, providing unrestricted access. It serves as a virtual space housing all institutional information, including reports and deliverables. The website will be kept online for at least 2 years after the end of the project.

Accountability

Developed and managed by ICONS, with input and feedback from ITeC and all the partners. Input and cooperation from ITeC and the rest of the RECONSTRUCT partnership will be encouraged during the project duration. To comply with General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the Data Controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by registered users upon online registration.

2.1. Graphic design

The reconstruct website was designed based on the project's visual identity that was proposed by ICONS and approved by the Project Coordinator, ITeC. First, the project's key target audiences were defined and discussed jointly, resulting in construction players (primary) and owners (secondary).

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Following a brand identity exercise that was carried out with ITeC, the main emerging reconstruct personality traits were the following: essential, popular, friendly, practical, and daring. Thus, two core ideas represented the foundations of reconstruct's identity system:

- Rounded and modular shapes as a key element representing the circular process of Reconstruct;
- Thin lines and geometric shapes to recall the style of technical drawing.

These concepts were applied to the project website. The following image shows the project homepage layout, which people see by accessing the URL. By scrolling down, the user can access the different pages or links to the Reconstruct internal pages. These can also be accessed from the menu bar.

Figure 1. Website home page

3. Contents and features

3.1. Landing page

Before the launch of the full website, a landing page was released in July 2023. This has served as a first digital presence and point of reference for the project's target audiences awaiting the launch of the full website. The page included different key elements:

- A brief description of the project and its main objectives
- Contact email of the project coordinator
- Access to the project's social media channels, namely LinkedIn and Twitter
- Possibility to register for the project's periodic e-newsletter

Additionally, the project launch press release was available for download on the main landing page.

The landing page layout is available in the figure below.

Accountability

Icons was responsible for the content production, the design and the development of the reconstruct landing page. The landing page content has been approved by ITeC before the launch.

Figure 2. RECONSTRUCT landing page

Circular territorial solutions for the built environment

Construction uses 32% of the world's natural resources and generates 25% of total solid waste. Hence, it is responsible for 40% of greenhouse gas emissions, of which more than a third come from embodied carbon in construction, especially from cement and steel.

The EU-funded project RECONSTRUCT aims to achieve circularity in the European construction sector to reduce the industry's strong environmental impact. To lower the use of primary non-renewable raw materials the project will:

- develop low-carbon alternatives to cement and steel;
- manufacture construction components that use recycled materials and are designed for modularity;
- embed deconstruction in building design.

The circular approach will be unleashed through digitisation and regionalisation of the construction value chain. Real-scale pilot buildings in Brussels and Barcelona will demonstrate the project's impact potential and economic feasibility.

For further information please contact the project coordinator:

Kathleen Blanco

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Join our journey towards a circular territorial for the built environment

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3.2. Website development and sections

The structure of the reconstruct website was created to allow an easy and intuitive navigation by the users.

The proposed structure is the following:

Section	Content description
Homepage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is the project website's main landing page. It features a prominent visual, a title, and a brief project description, with call-to-action links to relevant pages (e.g. "Discover more on our project" with a link to the "Project" section). In the upper part, the main navigation menu is always reachable, giving easy access to the website's main sections. The homepage displays the latest news, upcoming events, social feeds, project presentation video, and a newsletter subscription box.
Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This page contains a description of the project, aimed at visitors looking for a deeper level of technical and institutional information. It is divided into sub-sections or sub-paragraphs, describing objectives, technologies/solutions, project partners, fellow projects & CCRI. The consortium section is where the logos and contacts of each partner is displayed. The "Fellow projects" section is where we will list our sister projects from the cluster, with links to their websites. A specific section is dedicated to the CCRI.
Barcelona	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on the Barcelona demo building is included on an independent page. A Spanish translation of the text is included, together with the contact information of the main contact point.
Brussels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on the Brussels demo building is included on an independent page. The contact information of the main contact point is also available.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This section lists all the publications issued by the project available for consultation or download. It reports public deliverables and the RECONSTRUCT scientific papers published by project partners. The section may contain the graphic kit as well. This will consist of all graphic communication materials produced by the project: logos and brandbook, brochure, rollup, infopacks.... Resources can be filtered by categories.
News	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This section lists all the news about the project in inverse chronological order. News are divided into sub-categories, including updates, articles, interviews, press releases, newsletters, etc. In the main page visitors can read a short excerpt of the news and then go deeper on each news item's page.

Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section lists all the events organised or promoted by the project. Upcoming events are displayed first, followed by past events. • Each event has its own page and URL.
Stakeholder platform link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This button on the menu bar will directly lead to the stakeholder platform (once available), which is hosted on a different website and created by IRIS.

Contact information of the project coordinator and the communication secretariat is available in the footer, together with the short version of the disclaimer “co-funded by the European Union” and the EU flag. The full disclaimer is available by clicking on the “disclaimer” button, leading to a separate page where the full disclaimer is included.

Figure 3. Website tree map

RECONSTRUCT - Sitemap

4. Other features

The reconstruct website is optimized also for phone accessibility, thus increasing the number of potential users.

A dedicated button is available for users to subscribe to the reconstruct periodic e-newsletter. When registering, users are asked to accept the project's privacy notice, which is available in a dedicated section accessible from the website footer.

The website will also be the main access point to the project's stakeholder platform, which will be developed by IRIS.

The website footer hosts the EU emblem, jointly with the disclaimer. The links to reconstruct's social media channels, namely LinkedIn and Twitter, are included. Finally, direct contacts to reach the project coordinator and the communication secretariat are available, allowing interested audiences to get in contact for questions or collaborations.

5. Dissemination

Each Reconstruct partner is asked to give the highest visibility to the website, linking it to their company/organization institutional websites, disseminating it among their networks and referring to it in any communication concerning the project.

Sister projects, including Woodcircles and Circ-boost, have been asked to feature the reconstruct website link into their websites.

The website should also be included on the CCRI website.

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6. Conclusions

The RECONSTRUCT project will utilize the website as its main online communication tool to maintain online visibility and ensure the impact of its results. The project website adheres to the key visual elements developed for the project, ensuring consistency in communication tone and visual components across channels throughout the project's duration.

Constant collaboration with and from the consortium will be essential to ensure that the website achieves great visibility and is kept updated with the latest relevant news and information on the project.

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